

Effects of Audit Committee Size and Head on Audit Quality of Listed Consumer-Goods Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the effects of audit committees on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria over the period 2006–2016 using longitudinal research design. The population of the study is the twenty-three listed consumer-goods companies with the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2016. The sample size is fifteen after filtering eight companies listed outside the period of the study and without complete data set. The study uses secondary data from the published annual reports and accounts of sample firms. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the study. The results show that audit committee size has insignificant positive effect on audit quality; audit committee head shows mixed results (insignificant positive effect when audit quality is measured by audit firm size and insignificant negative effect when audit quality is measured by audit tenure). In view of these findings, the study concludes that audit committee size and head have no significant effect on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommends that consideration should not be given to size and head of audit committees when considering matters relating to audit quality.

Keywords: audit committee size, audit quality, consumer-goods companies, head.

1. Introduction

Audit committee is one arm of corporate governance mechanisms. The other is board of directors. Both are charged with oversight responsibility of financial reporting and disclosure among others. Audit committee head refers to the chairman of the committee who coordinate the activities of the committee. According to Hoitash and Hoitash (2009), the head of audit committee plays important roles of setting committee's agenda, working with committee members and serving as primary liaison between the

committee and board of directors, management and external auditor. Audit committee head is expected to have accounting, finance and business knowledge of the company in order to discharge his functions of planning, conducting committee meetings and overseeing audit quality of external auditor (Liesbeth, Ku, & Ganesh, 2015).

On the other hand, audit committee size refers to the number of members of the committee. In Nigeria, the maximum audit committee size for any listed company is six. The size of audit committee is expected to determine the needs and extent of delegated responsibilities of the committee. The purpose is to allow audit committee to function efficiently and all members participating freely based on individual diverse experience and knowledge.

Audit quality is an outcome of the performance of the audit team in planning, executing audit and the system of quality control of the audit firm as a whole (Miettinen, 2011). Audit quality involves a comprehensive understanding of the key risks that could impact on annual financial statements and translating that understanding into an effective audit plan to address those risks. Auditors are responsible for the quality of individual audit and ensure audit quality is consistently maintained. Audit quality is the assessment of whether audits have served both the shareholders and other stakeholders interests through increasing the accountability of managements and reinforcing trust and confidence in financial reporting.

The audit committee attributes of facilitating monitoring activities over external auditors in ensuring audit quality in this study are head and size of audit committee. The audit committee head is to organize and coordinate the committee meetings to review external auditor's audit planning and procedures to show how audit will be conducted in ensuring audit quality. The audit committee head with accounting expertise reflect valuable monitoring of external auditor outside regular meetings toward maintaining audit quality. Furthermore, audit committee size always determines the level of various divergent experiences, contributions and opinions of members during the committee's meeting and discussions with external auditor in ensuring audit quality.

Consumer-goods firms are companies producing finished products like food, beverages, alcoholic drinks, salt and foam. They were formally classified as listed food and beverages up till end of 2015. In 2016, the name of the sector changed to listed consumer-goods companies by expanding it from eighteen to twenty-three. The added companies are Unilever Nigeria Plc, PZ Cussions Nigeria Plc, Nigerian Enamelware Plc, DN Tyre and Rubber Plc and Vital Foam Nigeria Plc.

This study examines how audit committee attributes affect audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. There are many studies that have been carried out in Nigeria. For example, Bala (2014) examines audit committee characteristics and

earnings management of listed food and beverages firms in Nigeria. Also, Temple, Ofurum and Solomon (2016) examine audit committee characteristics and quality of financial reporting of quoted Nigerian banks. In an attempt to deviate from them, this study examines the effects of audit committee size and head on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. While Bala (2014) covers six years (2007-2012), Temple, Ofurum and Solomon (2016) cover 2014 firm year. This study covers eleven years (2006–2016).

Based on these, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested:

H₁: Audit committee size has no significant effect on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria; and

H₂: Audit committee head has no significant effect on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria.

The remaining part of this study consists of literature review, methodology, results and discussion, conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

According to Ibadin and Afensimi (2015), audit committee specializes in and is responsible for ensuring accuracy and reliability of financial statements provided by management. Audit committee serves as a liaison between the external auditor and the board of directors and facilitates monitoring process by reducing information asymmetry between external auditor and the board. This implies that audit committee serves as a bridge in the communication network between external auditors and board of directors. Audit committee helps to check activities of the auditors and top management resulting in bridging communication gap among users of financial statements (Atu, Atu, Atu, & Abusomwan, 2013).

Audit committee head is the functional and symbolic leader of the committee and he is expected to have accounting and financial expertise to enhance audit quality. The head of the audit committee plays a number of roles, including setting the agenda, working with audit committee members and serving as the primary liaison between the committee and the board of directors, management and external auditors (Liesbeth, Ku, & Ganesh, 2015). The accounting and financial expertise of audit committee head is to achieve audit quality through constructive criticism of external auditors.

The size of audit committee is an indication of resources available to it. Mohammed-Nor, Shafie and Wan-Hussin (2010) state that potential problems in auditing process are more likely to be uncovered and resolved with a larger audit committee. It implies that a larger audit committee size increases the resources

available to improve audit quality. Felo, Krishnamurthy and Solieri (2003) posit that a larger audit committee increases audit quality. Large audit committee members are more likely to discover and solve potential risks in auditing practices. Audit committee needs to have sufficient members so that different and informed views can be canvassed (Psaros, 2009).

According to DeAngelo (1981), audit quality is a market-assessed joint probability that a given auditor will discover a breach in the client's accounting system and report the breach. This definition emphasizes auditor's competence and independence to reflect audit quality. Audit quality could be a function of auditor's ability to detect material misstatements and reporting the errors (Seyyed, Mahdi, & Mohsen, 2013). Also, Bedard, Johnstone and Smith (2010) define audit quality as an audit conducted in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards to provide reasonable assurance that audited annual financial statements and related disclosures are presented in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles and are not materially misstated whether due to errors or fraud.

The theory relevant to this study is the stakeholders' theory. The theory proposes that the essence of corporate governance activities through establishment of audit committees is to ensure audit quality not only to benefit the shareholders but also other relevant stakeholders. Jensen (2001) states that a business would not be able to maximize shareholder value if any stakeholder is ignored and mistreated. The stakeholders include stockholders, creditors, suppliers, customers, employees, regulators and tax agencies. The maximization of shareholders' value is derived from the human and financial resources of the stakeholders. Stakeholders' theory is very important in the context of control mechanism adopted by the company through audit committee head and size in overseeing audit quality of external auditors that examine annual financial statements prepared by the management to ensure the interest of both shareholders and other stakeholders are pursued and protected.

Zheng (2008) examines the effect of audit committee head's financial expertise on audit quality. The study was conducted in USA with a sample size of 3,169 firms from 1997 to 2005 using multivariate regression technique. The result shows that audit committee head's financial expertise has significant positive effect on audit quality. Furthermore, Liesbeth, Ku and Ganesh (2015) interrogate the role of audit committee head's financial expertise and status in achieving audit quality. The study was conducted in UK using multiple regression technique on data from 3,824 public companies over the period (2004-2013). The finding shows that audit committee head's accounting expertise has insignificant positive effect on audit quality.

Yatim, Kent and Clarkson (2006) investigate the relationship between audit committee size and audit quality. The study uses multiple regression technique on data from 736 non-financial listed companies in Malaysia in the year 2003. The finding

reveals no significant relationship between audit quality and audit committee size. Zaman, Hudaib and Haniffa (2011) examine the effect of audit committee size on audit quality. The study uses 540 large and relatively small companies during the period (2001-2004) in UK. Ordinary Least Square regression model was used for the study. The result indicates significant positive relationship between audit committee size and audit quality.

3. Methodology

This study uses longitudinal research design. The population of the study consists of twenty three listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria as at 1st January, 2006 and remained listed up to 31st December, 2016. The sample size is fifteen selected based on two criteria: 5 companies were removed since they were listed after 1st January, 2006 and 3 companies were dropped due to incomplete data.

Descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlation and regression analysis) were used for the study. The study uses multiple regression technique to determine the effects of audit committee size and head on audit quality. Hausman specification test was conducted to determine the appropriate panel regression to use. Diagnostic tests such as heteroskedasticity test, multicollinearity test and normality test were used to test data quality. Ghafran (2013) models were used for the study as follows:

$$AQ1_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACS_{i,t} + \beta_2 ACH_{i,t} + \beta_3 CS_{i,t} + \beta_4 CC_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$AQ2_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACS_{i,t} + \beta_2 ACH_{i,t} + \beta_3 CS_{i,t} + \beta_4 CC_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Whereas:

AQ1 = Audit firm size; AQ2 = Audit tenure; ACS = Audit committee size; ACH = Audit committee head; CS = Company size; CC = Company complexity; β_0 = Intercept; β_{1-4} = Coefficient of independent variables; μ = Error term; i = companies and t = years.

This study uses audit firm size and audit tenure as proxies for audit quality as dependent variable since they are external auditors' attributes to audit quality in the published financial statements. The independent variables are the audit committee head and size while, control variables comprise of company size and company complexity to moderate audit quality.

AQ1 (firm size) is measured by the Big 4 audit firms such as KPMG, Ernst and Young, Price Water House Cooper and Akintola Williams Delloittee and non Big 4 firms. Audit quality is equal to one (1) if a company is audited by one of the Big 4 audit firms and zero (0) if otherwise (Miettinen, 2011). AQ2 stands for auditor's tenure and is measured by the number of years spent as external auditor with the client. Auditor's

tenure of above three years equal one (1) and zero (0) if otherwise as used by Okolie (2014). ACS that stands for audit committee size is measured by the total number of members serving on the audit committee per year (Temple, Ofurum, & Solomon, 2010). While ACH which is audit committee head is measured by one (1) for audit committee headed by financial and accounting expertise and Zero (0) for audit committee headed by non financial and accounting expertise (Zheng, 2008). CS stands for company size is measured by natural logarithm of total assets of the company (Bala, 2014). CC that represents company complexity is measured by total number of company's manufacturing plants outside Headquarters (Lifschutz, Jacob, & Feldshtein, 2010). β_0 stands for intercept; β_{1-4} represents coefficients of independent variables; μ stands for error term; i represents companies and t stands for years.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
AQ1	165	0.7848	0.3913	0	1
AQ2	165	0.7030	0.4583	0	1
ACS	165	5.7333	0.6260	4	6
ACH	165	0.7030	0.4583	0	1
CS	165	9.5760	1.9949	4.220	12.815
CC	165	3.2788	3.1691	1	12

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data

Audit quality (AQ1) measured by audit firm size in Table 1 indicates mean value of 0.7848; standard deviation value of 0.3913; minimum value of 0 and maximum value of 1. It means on average 78.48% of listed consumer-goods companies are audited by the Big 4 audit firms with wide dispersion of 39.13% from the mean. Similarly, Audit quality (AQ2) measured by auditors' tenures with dichotomous variables of 0 and 1 showing minimum of three (3) years and above three (3) years respectively. The mean value of 0.7030 indicates that 70.30% of the auditors of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria spent above three (3) years in office. While Standard deviation value of 0.4583 indicate little wide dispersion from mean.

On audit committee size (ACS), the mean value of 5.7333 is an indication of about six (6) members of audit committee on average of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. The minimum and maximum values of 4 and 6 indicate audit committee membership respectively. Audit committee head (ACH) on the other hand indicate minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1 that signify audit committees are headed by non accounting and accounting expertise respectively. The mean value of

0.7030 is an indication that 70.30% on average of listed consumer-goods companies' audit committees are headed by financial and accounting expertise. The standard deviation value of 0.4583 indicates wide dispersion from mean.

The control variable of natural logarithm of company size (CS) indicates minimum and maximum values of 4.2195 and 12.8149 respectively. The mean value is 9.5760 while standard deviation value of 1.9949 indicates wide dispersion from mean. On the company complexity (CC), the minimum and maximum values are 1 and 12 respectively. The mean and standard deviation values of 3.2788 and 3.1691 indicate no dispersion from mean.

The correlation matrix presents the relationship between variables of the study as contained in Table 2.

Table 2

Correlation Matrix

Variable	AQ1	AQ2	ACS	ACH	CS	CC
AQ1	1.0000					
AQ2	0.0496	1.0000				
	0.5273					
ACS	-0.1361	-0.0014	1.0000			
	0.0814	0.9856				
ACH	0.0836	-0.0741	0.0836	1.0000		
	0.2860	0.3444	0.2857			
CS	0.5709	0.0343	0.2401	0.0655	1.0000	
	0.0000	0.6615	0.0019	0.4035		
CC	-0.1333	-0.098	0.2559	0.0112	0.4702	1.0000
	0.087	0.9004	0.0009	0.8868	0.0000	

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data

ACS has insignificant negative relationship with AQ1 (coef. = -0.1361, p-value = 0.0814) and AQ2 (coef. = -0.0014, p-value = 0.9856). Also, ACH has insignificant positive relationship with AQ1 (coef. = 0.0836, p-value = 0.2860). It also has insignificant negative relationship with AQ2 (coef. = -0.0741, p-value = 0.3444). Similarly, CS has significant positive relationship with AQ1 (coef. = 0.5709, p-value =

0.0000) but insignificant positive relationship with AQ2 (coef. = 0.0343, p-value = 0.6615). Also, CC has significant negative relationship with AQ1 though at 10% (coef. = -0.1333, p-value = 0.087) and insignificant negative relationship with AQ2 (coef. = -0.098, p-value = 0.9004).

Table 3 presents the values of VIF and 1/VIF of independent and control variables of the study.

Table 3

Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
CC	1.32	0.756257
CS	1.31	0.761020
ACS	1.10	0.910961
ACH	1.01	0.989643
Mean VIF	1.19	

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data.

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) values which should be between 1 and 4 and tolerance values (1/VIF) of less than 1 test multicollinearity in data. The VIF values of 1.32; 1.31; 1.10 and 1.01 are for variables CC; CS; ACS and ACH respectively. The tolerance values indicate 0.756257; 0.761020; 0.910961 and 0.989643 for CC; CS; ACS and ACH respectively. The VIF mean is 1.19. The autocorrelation level of data for study may not have any statistical significant impact as indicated by values of VIF and 1/VIF.

Table 4

Shapiro-Wilk W Test

Variable	Observation	Prob>z
AQ1	165	0.00016
AQ2	165	0.28265
ACS	165	0.00000
ACH	165	0.28265
CS	165	0.00000
CC	165	0.00000

Source: STATA 11 Output based on study data (See appendix A).

Table 4 presents the results of Shapiro–Wilk test for normal data at 5% level of significance for all variables. Data sets for AQ2 and ACH are normally distributed as indicated by Prob>z values of 0.28265 and 0.28265 respectively which are not significant. On the other hand, AQ1, ACS, CS and CC data sets are not normally distributed as shown by Prob>z values of 0.00016; 0.00000; 0.00000 and 0.00000

which are significant. The lack of normal distribution of variables data sets requires application of robust regression technique.

Table 5 shows the heteroskedasticity test for appropriateness of OLS regression for the study.

Table 5

Breusch-pagan / Cook-weisberg Test

Variable	Chi2 (1)	Prob>chi2
AQ1	18.94	0.0000
AQ2	97.67	0.0000

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data.

The decision rule for Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test of heteroskedasticity states that when Prob>Chi² value is significant; the data sets show presence of heteroskedasticity. But, there is absence of hettest if the value of Prob>Chi² is not significant. AQ1 (Model 1) heteroskedasticity test indicates Chi²(1) value of 18.94 which is significant with Prob>chi² value of 0.0000. Hence, the AQ1 data set is heteroskedastic. AQ2 (Model 2) heteroskedasticity test shows Chi²(1) value of 97.67 which is also significant at Prob>chi² value of 0.0000. In the same vein, AQ2 data is also heteroskedastic. All the results of heteroskedastic tests show presence of hettest indicating OLS regressions are not appropriate for the two models.

Table 6

Hausman Specification Test

Model	Chi ² (4)	Prob>chi ²
AQ1	43.88	0.0000
AQ2	20.21	0.0005

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data.

Hausman Specification test in Table 6 is conducted to choose between FE and RE regressions. The decision rule indicates that if the value of Hausman specification test is significant, FE regression is most appropriate. But if Prob>chi² is not significant, RE regression is most appropriate. Model 1 Hausman specification test reveals Chi²(4) value of 43.88 with Prob>chi² value of 0.0000 which is significant, hence, FE regression is used. On the other hand, Model 2 Hausman specification test also indicates Chi²(4) value of 20.21 with Prob>chi² value of 0.0005 which is significant, FE regression is adopted.

Table 7

Model 1 FE Regression Result

AQ1	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t	P> t
ACS	0.0772346	0.0418874	1.84	0.086
ACH	0.010266	0.0213425	0.48	0.638
CS	0.0489522	0.0527837	0.93	0.369
CC	-0.0108841	0.0080189	-1.36	0.196
Constant	-0.0982624	0.3595585	-0.27	0.789
R ²		0.3231	Adj R ²	0.2567
F-Statistics		3.51	Prob>F	0.0348
Hausman Specification Test Chi ²	43.88		P>Chi ²	0.0000

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data.

As shown in Table 7, the Hausman specification test for Model 1 shows value of $P>chi^2 = 0.0000$ which is significant at 5% indicating adoption of FE regression. The FE regression is also robust due to lack of normal distribution of some data based on the Shapiro-Wilk test (See Table 4). The robust FE regression result is fitted as evidenced by F-Statistics value of 3.51 with Prob>F value of 0.0348 which is significant at 5%.

ACS under Model 1 has t-value of 1.84 and $P>|t|$ value of 0.086 at 5% level of significance. It means that audit committee size has insignificant positive effect on audit quality. Also, ACH has t-value of 0.48 with $P>|t|$ value of 0.638 at 5% level of significance. This is an indication that audit committee head has insignificant positive effect on audit quality. Table 8 shows model 2 that has audit quality (AQ2) measured by audit tenures as dependent variable. Independent variables include Audit Committee Size (ACS) and Audit Committee Head (ACH). Control variables are Company Complexity (CC) and natural logarithm of Company Size (CS).

Table 8

Model 2 FE Regression Result

AQ2	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t	P> t
ACS	0.0450332	0.1228067	0.37	0.719
ACH	-0.076722	0.0690811	-1.11	0.285
CS	0.2065492	0.0577681	3.58	0.003

CC	-0.0721298	0.0106627	-6.76	0.000
Constant	-1.2426648	0.7671452	-1.62	0.128
R ²		0.2424	Adj R ²	0.0026
F-Statistics		15.68	Prob>F	0.0000
Hausman Specification Test Chi ²	20.21		P>Chi2	0.0005

Source: STATA 11 Outputs based on study data.

The Hausman specification test in Table 8 shows Prob>chi² value of 0.0005 which is significant at 5% level of significance indicates appropriateness of FE regression for Model 2 which is robust due to lack of normal distribution of some of the data based on Shapiro-wilk test for normal data (See Table 4). The robust FE regression result shows independent variables ACS and ACH t-values of 0.37 and -1.11 that signified positive and negative effects of audit committee size and head respectively on audit quality. The ACS and ACH values of P>|t| are 0.719 and 0.285 respectively at 5% level of significance. These are indications that audit committee size and head have insignificant effects on audit quality measured by auditors' tenures in listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria.

On the test of hypothesis (H₁), the findings of the two models reveal insignificant effect of audit committee head on audit quality measured by audit firm size and auditors' tenures. Hence, the null hypothesis that audit committee head has no significant effect on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria is hereby accepted. The result did not agree with the study of Zheng (2008) but agreed with the study of Liesbeth, Ku and Ganesh (2015). This is an indication that most of the audit committees are not being headed by financial and accounting expertise in listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria.

Furthermore, the second hypothesis (H₂) test reveals insignificant effect of audit committee size on audit quality. Therefore, the study has no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The result agreed with the study of Yatim, Kent and Clarkson (2006) but disagreed with the study of Hudaib and Haniffa (2011). The insignificant effect of audit committee size on audit quality may not be unconnected with the present maximum size of six members per company's audit committee which might not be adequate to address all auditing issues in listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examines the effects of audit committee size and head on audit quality. Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that audit committee size and head

have no significant effects on audit quality of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. The study recommends that audit committee size and head should not be a matter of concern in the constitution of audit committees by consumer-goods firms in Nigeria.

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